

ISic1035

I.Sicily inscription 1035

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list

Material

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6795

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]NTOΣ[---]
2. [---]ς Φιλ[---]
3. [---]ίδας Φιλ[---]
4. [---]ινίλας Ἡρα[---]
5. [---]στοκλῆς Πο[---]

Apparatus

Text of Pugliese Carratelli 1956

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644932

PHI 175413

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0214a (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 030a

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 389

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.4 tav.34

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